

Hero Stones from Palamaner Mandal of Chittoor District,

Andhra Pradesh: A Historical Study

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ABSTRACT

Hero stones, in factual sense regarded as one of the means of remembering deceased persons who perhaps devoted their life for the cause of the society irrespective of caste, status, religion and creed. The word Hero- Stone is described in various sources as stone image, Veerakallu (in Telugu), Nadukal(in Tamil), Veeragallu(in Kannada), Veeragal(in Marathi), etc., as ‘Veera’ mean a ‘Warrior’ and ‘Kallu’ or ‘Gallu’ mean ‘Stone’, which has been derived from two languages- ‘Veera’ from Sanskrit and Kallu from Kannada.

Palamaner (13.2000°N; 78.7500°E), a Mandal head quarters with population of 51,165 and a total population of 81,470 (2011 census) inhabiting in 15 village panchayaths with an extent of 79.50 sq.km. lies in the north, north-east of Baireddipalli Mandal, west to Bangarupalam Mandal, south of Gangavaram Mandal and forms border to Tamil Nadu and Karnataka States in the east and west respectively and Venkatagiri Kota Mandal lies to its south. It is drained by Kaudinya river in its north-eastern corner adjoining the eastern hill-forest cover zone which is famous for elephants sanctuary. Being close to Karnataka and Tamil Nadu States border people here bear a mixed culture.

The present paper deals with 10 hero stones found at 7 villages in the Palamaner mandal of Chittoor district. These are varied in nature as some of them poses hero fighting a tiger, hero shooting at a lion , hero with a sati and hero with animals and birds. These are analysed into 10 categories of broad perspective.

Key Words: Hero Stones, Palamaner Mandal, Categories in Hero Stones

Introduction:

The word ‘hero stone’ is a form of compound comprising a single slab or group of slabs connected to form a shrine erected in honor of individual/s who have perished in certain range

of circumstances while carrying out a community protection or sacrificial deed. Normally they bear an iconographical and epigraphic apparatus which provides information on the identity of the deceased and the context of his death. It is to be noted that the expression 'hero-stones' somehow sound over the variety of terms with which Indian languages designate these panels. Such a variety is not just a matter pertaining to linguistic domain; rather it reflects the formal and structural changes of materials according to the area where they were produced. A series of etymologically related words like *vīragal* in Marathi, *vīrakkal* in Tamil, *vīragallu* in Kannada, *vīrakallu* in Telugu are the literary counterparts of 'hero-stone'. Terms like *chāyāstambha*, proper of the specimens from Andhra Pradesh (Murthy 1982: 210) or *khambha*, and its alternative forms like *khamba* and *khambhi* are diffused in Northern and Central India (Sontheimer 1982: 92; Shah 1982: 102) which convey the meaning of shade-pillar and pillar, with reference to a memorial in shape. From Gujarat and Rajasthan the terms *Pāliya* and *Govardhana* are allowed instead to the concept of protection (i.e. a memorial to the protector of the community) as the root of the first term (Doshi 1982: 165-166). Their iconographic repertoire suggests that the second term namely *Kṛiṣṇa Govardhanadhara* shows its importance (Agrawala 1982: 151).

Even though the general pattern of describing a memorial being erected in remembering the valor of a hero for his sacrifice to the society or due to his service to his master, etc. being recognized as a memorial meant exclusively erected for him. This is a specific category of hero stone with or without inscription has some meaning in the basic concept of heroism. It can be further divided into Hero stone, Sati stone and Sati-cum-Hero stone depending on the sculptural representation being noticed and its form changes through period of time at different levels of its erection which is related to the status of the hero as well as to the action performed by him.

Some of the rituals and beliefs connected with the hero stones in the past and at present would help us in interpreting that the hero cult continued to survive for a considerable period of time and even now they are well preserved in different localities where they are found. Erecting hero stone was basically part of the ritual connected with hero cult. The present scholar has observed that this cult seems to be popularly followed in several parts of South India. Folklore connected with many such heroes as a part of their cult is also common in this area. Such practices help us to infer about the nature of hero cult of historical importance during bygone periods.

The Area:

Palamaner (13.2000°N; 78.7500°E), a Mandal head quarters with population of 51,165 and a total population of 81,470 (2011 census) inhabiting in 15 village panchayaths with an extent of 79.50 sq.km. lies in the north, north-east of Baireddipalli Mandal, west to Bangarupalam Mandal, south of Gangavaram Mandal and forms border to Tamil Nadu and Karnataka States in the east and west respectively and Venkatagiri Kota Mandal lies to its south. It is drained by Kaudinya river in its north-eastern corner adjoining the eastern hill-forest cover zone which is famous for elephants' sanctuary. Being close to Karnataka and Tamil Nadu States border people here bear a mixed culture. Palamaner mandal has has a total number of 15 village panchayats and 82 hamlets and only 7 villages in the present survey have given the evidence of 10 hero stones. Two of these hero stones are found in temples located at Palamaner and Kurmai.

1.Chethapenta (13°.08942'N; 78°.72758'E)

This village is situated in the Bayyappagaripalli panchayath, at a distance of 6 km. from Mandapeta Koturu and 8 km. to Nellapatla village of Baireddipalli, another Mandal Head Quarters which is close to Tamil Nadu border with forest cover in which the village population rear their animal folk and gather firewood, if any.

Fig.1: Hero fighting a tiger with spear.

About 4 km. north of this village, in the forest area, one can reach an irrigation tank namely 'Cherapa Cheruvu' and close to this tank towards east a hero stone (Fig.1: 136 x 109 x 20 cm.) lies which contains Hero holding a spear in his both arms fighting at the tiger. He has crest hair style, distinct upper garment and thick cloth belt encircling waist and below which but behind the waist a broad cloth is held up to his knees as lower garment He has a quiver hanging behind his left shoulder with a number of arrows in it. He did not wear ornaments on his body and one

can notice a dead body of a tiger lying in front of him on the ground indicating that he was engaged on hunting wild animals in view of protecting people and domestic animals.

2. Kurmai (13°.16306 'N; 78°.73822 'E)

This village is situated at about 6 km. away from Palamaner at the border of Tamil Nadu State in the Pengaragunta village panchayath. A temple dedicated to Lord Varadarajaswamy lies on the right bank of Kaudinya river. According to a local legend during Muslim invasions the temple was subjected to destruction, hence Hindu devotees have hidden its parts underneath the river bed and it is believed that the God flee to Kanchi. While doing so his foot prints got imprinted on a stone and when the river receives water during monsoon, the temple gets afloat. The local people believe that the temple was reconstructed where it afloat. A Siva Linga was found towards west of the temple while ploughing over which t present temple being built. Every year in September-October Jatara (fair) is celebrated here and the present scholar located two hero stones on the boundary wall of this temple as given below:

Fig.2: Hero with bow and arrow in action.

The first hero stone (Fig.2: 110 x 94 x 14 cm) contains Hero with bow and arrow in action as he positioned the arrow in the bow by his left hand stretched back. A quiver is seen at the back his left shoulder and kept his right leg straight whereas left leg bent according to shooting method. Upper garment is indistinct over the body and Dhoti formed lower garment covered up to knees supported by a string at the waist. There is a sheath of sword hanging over the waist. He has distinct knot hair style held at the back of his head.

Fig.2a: Hero shooting at a lion.

The second hero stone shows (Fig.2a: 122 x 97 x 16 cm) Hero shooting at the lion with bow and arrow held in his right and left hands respectively. He possessed knotted hair style held at his head back and lower garment 'Dhoti' spread on both legs with bracelets over wrists. His left leg is stepped front whereas right leg behind.

Lion is depicted with raised forelimbs and hind limbs being kept on the ground. Its tail is prominently shown encircled at the end.

3. Musalimadugu (Fig.3: 13°.15092' N;78°. 77861' E)

This village is situated 6 km. away from Palamaneru at the border of Tamil Nadu State in the Pengaragunta panchayath. There is a hero stone lying on the left side of road leading to Gudiyattam from Musalimadugu village in the field of Venkata Rami Reddy, a resident of the same village.

Fig.3: A woman in sitting posture.

It is a single slab on which a female figure is depicted in sitting posture over which a shrine was constructed and worshipped locally known as 'Uchchu Mallamma' or 'Yellamma', being depicted with bun hair style but tied at the head back on the right side. She sat with her two legs

folded on either sides and her drapery cannot be seen clearly perhaps due to weathering of rock. But her breast are prominently depicted and perhaps covered with blouse as upper garment below which lies the waist prominently shown. Her face is broad with prominent eye-brows, nose and other facial features. Several dots of vermilion and turmeric at intervals on the body of this female hero indicating that she is periodically worshipped by the villagers for their prosperity and well being.

Two legends prevail in the area about the present hero stone. The first one is that Uchchu Mallamma was a valour woman who participated in battle fields, hence protected the village from wild animals. When Punganur Jamindar insisted her to pay tax, she went on a tiger and fought with him. She also fought with oxen and she used to command wood apple tree to drop its fruits and reconnect them through her simple thumb noise. Another legend goes that when a boy was going on his way with bullocks was beaten by village herdsmen and when the boy complained this matter to Uchchu Mallamma, she got angry and blocked the way of herdsmen, hence their bullock carts did not move. When the herdsmen begged her pardon, they were excused and the obstruction got removed. The village people worship her by offering boiled gram rice and as this place is close to forest area where wild elephants move around, hence government of Andhra Pradesh declared it as Kaundinya wild elephant sanctuary.

4. Palamaner (13°. 19895'N; 78°.7447'E)

This place is a Mandal Head Quarters situated on the Chittoor-Bangalore National High way and there is a temple dedicated to Lord Venugopalaswamy in Patapeta locality in the Palamaneru town known as Nagulakunta near to which was a well-known abode for Cobras. There are two hero stones at this place as described below.

Fig. 4: A panel of three pair of Hero and Sati.

The first hero stone is a panel (Fig.4: 58 x 126 x 48 cm.) being found attached to the western boundary wall of the temple on its south-western direction. It has three pairs of Hero and Sati figures in standing posture. In the first pair, Hero poses bow and arrow in action and to his right stand. Sati with a vertical object in her right hand. Both have dressed hair style and the Hero wore 'Dhoti' as lower garment up to knees and a crown is seen over his head. In the second pair, the Hero is similar to that of the first Hero but has a quiver on his left shoulder

back and possessed crest hair style. To his right stands Sati with high necked jar (pitcher) in her left hand and blessing the Hero with her right hand. She has bun hair style. The third pair is similar to that of first pair that the Hero is shooting an arrow with a bow in action who possessed crest hair style. Sati stands right to him holding a pitcher in her left hand and blessing the Hero with her right hand.

Fig.4a. Hero on the horse with Siva Linga in front.

The second hero stone (Fig.4a: 140 x 71 x 15 cm.) lies at the Municipal office of Palamaneru town situated in Lord Eswara temple street. Hero is shown riding a horse, wearing a chain in his neck without upper garment but Dhoti formed the lower garment. There is a sheath of sword hanging from his waist. He has crest hair

style and large ear lobes from which hangs large rings. A Siva Linga is seen in front of the horse. The horse is well decorated with riding equipment such as bridle and saddle. A Siva Ling and flowers are depicted being thrown over it. It seems that the Palamaner area was under the rule of Pallava kings as its ancient name had been 'Palavan Yeri' according to local legend and during the course of time it has been modified as Palamaner.

5. Syagandram (Fig.5: 13°.11521'N; 78°.76011'E)

This is a hamlet of seven households situated in the Mandipetakotur panchayath on Kalavapalli-Mandipeta road close to forest area. There is a hero stone (dolmen) located towards south of the village proper in the field belonging to S.Babu, of the same hamlet.

Fig.5: Hero with spear, two Sati to his left.

It contains (Fig.5: 124 x 121 x 16 cm.) a Hero and two Sati figures. The Hero is held with a spear in his two arms. He has a turban on his head and remaining lower part of his hair is seen falling over his neck back. Both arms have two bracelets each over elbow and upper arms. Below the shoulders there is a bag like object in the shape of fish, with indistinct upper garment

and his waist is covered with cloth in the form of wearing dhoti being dressed like a village fellow as seen even today. The lower garment with border is tied at its end on his left leg. Two Sati figures are shown standing behind the Hero among which the first Sati raised her right hand with a flower and kept her left hand over waist. She has bun hair style, tight blouse, bracelets on both arms and ear rings. She wore sari up to feet with longitudinal fold across middle of legs. Whereas, the second Sati stands straight with her right hand with five fingers depicted clearly. Her sari border is touching her feet and stood left to first Sati. This hero stone is being worshipped by the local farmers before sowing seeds, hence a boundary wall is constructed around it for protection.

6. T.S. Agraharam (13°.1834' N; 78°.75395')

Fig.6: Hero with sword and an unidentified object.

This village is situated at 4 km. south of Palamaner town on the Mandapetakotur road which can be approached by a cart-track. There is a famous old temple dedicated to Lord Subrahmanya situated on top of a hill nearby. Devotees with a wooden 'kavadi' is presented whenever they visit the temple as part of fulfilling their vows. There is a hero stone (Fig.6: Hero with a sword and an unidentified object: 49 x 54 x 14 cm.) located underneath a fig tree found along with another sculpture of a God. The Hero has bun hair style held behind his head, ear rings and holds a sword in his right hand held high over his right shoulder and an unidentified object is seen in his left fist held down. His lower and upper garments are invisible but there is a waist belt held across the waist. The whole hero stone is decorated with vermillion dots.

7. Thavadapalli (13°.16835' N; 78°.74352'E)

This village is situated 4 km. from Palamaner town in the Vaddur panchayath and the scholar has located two hero stones in the field of P.Lakshminarayana, of the same village underneath a tamarind tree in a mango garden located on one of the banks of Kaundinya river on the way to Samudrapalli.

Fig.7: Hero with sword and shield, man, cow, deer and bull; pigeon and parrot.

The first hero stone (Fig.7: 325 x 153 x 11 cm.) contains Hero with sword in his right hand and shield in his left hand, possessing crest hair style. He has bracelets over his arms and indistinct upper garment but ‘Dhoti’ forms the lower garment spread below waist up to knees by covering both thighs, however border of it being spread between legs. There is a man below the Hero figure holding a sword and a shield in his right and left hands respectively. There are many animal figures depicted, in small size, such as deer, cow, and bull in sitting posture whereas dove and parrot are shown flying. The deer has no horns and its body is depicted with dot designs.

Fig.7a: Hero fighting a tiger.

The second hero stone (Fig.7a: 127 x 120 x 12 cm) contains Hero fighting a tiger. Hero has crest hair style tied above the head, a chain in the neck, without ear rings and upper garment. His waist is encircled with a cloth belt over which is attached a sheath of sword. He held the animal’s head in his left hand, trying to pierce sword into it with his right hand.

Discussion:

In the present survey, hero stones are categorised into 10 categories.

Which are mentioned as below:

C1. Hero fighting a tiger with a spear .C2. Hero with a bow and an arrow in action .C3. Hero shooting at a lion. C4. A woman (Female Hero) in sitting posture (Uchchu mallamma or Yellamma, a local Goddess). C5. A panel of three pair of Hero and sati. C6. Hero on the horse with Siva Linga in front. C7. Hero with spear, two sati to his left. C8. Hero with a sword and an unidentified object. C9. Hero with sword and shield, man, cow, deer, bull, pigeon and parrot.C10. Hero fighting a tiger.

Number of hero stones are reported from adjoining Punganur taluk as well as Tamil Nadu State. Most of them are found as similar to the hero stones reported from the present area.

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